

CASE STUDY OF A LARGE SCALE DFAN TEST: PART ONE

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Abstract

Building on previously published studies focusing on the validation and qualification of a novel method of Direct Field Acoustic Testing, this paper presents a case study of the recent execution of a large Direct Field Acoustic Test. It is intended to be circumspect of all aspects of the test process. It not only discusses in-depth technical topics and acoustical results, but it also provides a holistic review of the entire test campaign. This includes but is not limited to pre-test planning, logistical considerations, mechanical operations, system configuration, structural stability considerations, and human safety considerations.

Introduction

First utilized in the 1990's as a method for performing acoustic testing utilizing high-powered loudspeakers instead of reverberant chambers [1], the Direct Field Acoustic Testing (DFAN) method has continued to grow in both capability and popularity. While the late-2000's saw the introduction of what would become the initial practices for utilizing concert loudspeakers to perform flight-level acoustic testing, the methodology reached an inflection point with the adoption of DFAN for testing of the Orion Crew Module and Service Module elements [2], and the issuance of the NASA Handbook 7010 for DFAN testing in 2016 [3].

While a great deal of data has been published describing the performance, acoustic field, and structural excitation provided by different approaches to DFAN testing, little has been published to illuminate the inner workings of a complete DFAN test campaign from start to finish. Equally critical to the success of a DFAN campaign as correct microphone placements or safe structural excitation, DFAN system design, installation, verification, and operation are all key aspects of a successful and safe DFAN campaign. Unfortunately, these topics are typically overlooked in the catalog of published works available on DFAN testing today.

A large-format DFAN test was selected as a candidate for a case study. An emphasis was made on providing a complete 360-degree review of the

logistical, operational, and technical aspects of: Pre-test design, installation, configuration, testing, data analysis, and verifying results. While the goal of the case study is primarily to provide measurable, technical data to quantify real-world DFAN system performance, successful execution of the key operational steps outlined above are critical to ensuring that a DFAN test can be performed successfully, safely, and to the complete satisfaction of the test requirements.

3. PRE-TEST CONSIDERATIONS

One of the first steps taken upon selection of the DFAN test methodology for performing an acoustic test is the design of the DFAN test system configuration. The primary driver for this design process is the size and shape of the device under test (DUT), as the envelope of the DUT informs the DFAN test system size, the diameter of the complete test setup, and the placement of ancillary equipment such as amplifier racks, power cabling, and data acquisition racks. Best practices developed over the last several years have shown the importance of developing an acoustic field that envelops the axial and vertical extents of the DUT [4], with physical margin around and above the DUT to ensure uniform acoustic coverage, as well as safe working space for technicians during testing.

Figure 1: 2D CAD of DFAN test configuration, test article extents shown as 3.35M circle in center.

One of the most common initial considerations to arise from the design of a DFAN system configuration is simply ensuring the system will fit in the space provided. A significant benefit to the DFAN methodology is that it can be deployed in a variety of different locations. However, this means that every location a DFAN test is to be conducted in must be capable of physically fitting the system and its supporting equipment into the space provided, as well as

ensuring room is available for technicians, flight hardware movements, and safety walkways.

Important to note in these initial design discussions are three key areas that can cause significant challenges to a test campaign if not properly reviewed and designed in advance of the test itself:

1. The Concept of Operations (ConOps) of where columns of acoustic devices can be lifted, moved, and stored when the test circle needs to be opened for the installation of the DUT.
2. The safety and stability of independently placed, stored columns that are not in use while the DUT is being installed and stability of the partially constructed DFAN system with columns removed.
3. The entire step-by-step process of breaking configuration, installing flight hardware, and restoring configuration following installation.

While not a specific single operation, item #3 in the prior list becomes increasingly critical as the DFAN test setup and DUT become larger, especially when large relative to the size of the physical test facility. If a thorough review of critical lifts, spacecraft movements, floor space available, temporary cable paths, and partial configuration stability is not undertaken, it significantly increases the risk of operational challenges and delays during the test campaign.

With the selection of a vertical height to support the DUT, large, tall configurations such as the one described in this case study will require a detailed structural analysis. The goal of this analysis is to understand not only the susceptibility of column of acoustic devices to a potential over-turning event, but also the behavior of the entire DFAN system as it is deployed and potentially joined together to provide additional structural reinforcement. While the topic of structural stability is mentioned in published documents such as the NASA HDBK-7010, that document in particular mentions that an analysis should be performed but provides no industry-accepted standards or processes to assist in the creation of a safe and stable configuration [3].

This shortage of guidance led the team to compile a set of internal reference standards [5] based on published, accepted industry standards. Selected examples being:

- National Aeronautics and Space Administration, NASA-STD-5005D
- American Society of Civil Engineers ASCE 7-16 Minimum Design Loads and Associated Criteria for Buildings and Other Structures (2016)

- American Institute of Steel Construction (AISC), Steel Construction Manual 15th Edition (2017)
 - Chapter B – Design Requirements
 - Chapter C – Design for Stability
- American Wood Council, National Design Specification (NDS) for Wood Construction (2018)

Following a comprehensive review of these documents by a qualified structural engineer, and an internal review of previously utilized best practices and areas for improvement from previous DFAN test campaigns, several internal requirements were developed. These would help guide the design process to ensure the delivery of a robust, safe configuration that applied appropriate conservatism, while models were generated (Figure 2) to help identify and quantify potential risks. Minimum or maximum design requirements for Factor of Safety (FoS), Vertical Loads, Lateral Loads, Seismic Loads, Tipping Design Limit Loads were generated.

Figure 2: An 8x6 DFAN system shown in RISA 3D for analysis prior to the test described in this case study.

The resultant DFAN test system design, structural load models, and associated calculations were assembled into a pre-test system configuration and facility impact report. Often a DFAN test can occur in a facility that is not under the exclusive control of the DFAN test vendor or spacecraft prime contractor, so additional parties may need to review the report for the purpose of inquiry, comment, and ensuring compliance to facility policies and procedures. The generation of a thorough, detailed, and understandable structural design report is critical for ensuring that all parties understand the design elements, constraints, and safe operating modes of the DFAN test system physical configuration.

4. PREPARATION & DESIGN OF DFAN SYSTEM

With the previously discussed considerations in mind, a 6.6m tall DFAN system was designed to test a payload just over 5m in height and 3.4m in diameter.

For this case study, there are three areas of note from the viewpoint of DFAN test preparation and system layout:

1. Hierarchy of priorities when selecting equipment and interconnect locations.
2. The reasoning behind placement of various runs of different types of cabling.
3. Implementation of a remote, combined DFAN control & data acquisition system (DAS).

4.1 Hierarchy of Priorities

A hierarchy of priorities can help inform the decisions that arise when a DFAN system needs to be designed for placement into a given area. While it is a relatively simple exercise to draw a picture of where acoustic devices should be placed in a room, the placement of acoustic devices is only a portion of the complete test system configuration. The pathways for a significant amount of loudspeaker cabling, power cabling, microphone cabling, and all interconnect points associated with the respective cables need to be considered. Additionally, the cabling for the acoustic test system can potentially cross paths with cabling and ground support equipment required for the unit under test. This itself is a key consideration in the process of system design and deployment, as the acoustic test system and cabling need to be deployed for optimal operation, as well as support the efficient installation, testing, and removal of the test article from the test circle.

4.2 Determining Cable Pathways

The following hierarchy was utilized to help determine locations for cable pathways and support equipment:

1. Personnel Safety
 - a. Safe access to the test circle
 - b. Safe pathways around the test setup
 - c. Trip hazards created by complete or temporary system configurations
 - d. Limiting overhead work
2. Facility Safety
 - a. Easily controlled entry/exit points
 - b. Clearly marked walkways for test and non-test personnel
 - c. Levels estimated for working areas

3. Flight Hardware Safety
 - a. Clear paths to move hardware
 - b. Adequate clearance in the test circle
 - c. Minimize critical lifts

With these considerations in mind, and following diligent collaboration between the test service provider, the spacecraft prime contractor, and the facility support staff (including relevant Authorities Having Jurisdiction, AHJ's), the following pathways (Figure 3) were identified. These were the ideal locations to run the cabling required to operate the system, as well as the optimal locations of the support hardware required for test operations, while respecting the areas dedicated to personnel walkways. The development of Figure 3 ensured all parties (test vendor, spacecraft prime, facility support personnel) could review, approve, and support the cable pathways.

Figure 3: Plan for cable pathways around setup. Note safe egress paths around outer perimeter.

4.3 Combined Control & Data Acquisition System

Another key topic for this campaign was the development and implementation of a combined DFAN control and large-scale Data Acquisition System (DAS) solution, operated remotely via fiber optic transport. Validated as an effective solution in smaller configurations prior to this campaign, the goals of implementing this large-format simultaneous control + DAS solution were:

1. Simplify the post-test data processing and analysis process by providing all time histories for acoustic test microphones and test article sensors in one single data package, with all inputs sample aligned.
2. Reduce the amount of hardware required by eliminating the need for two separate systems.

3. Enable the use of a high bandwidth fiber optic connection, placing the DAS inputs at the test setup, and significantly reducing the distance analog sensor cables needed to run from the test circle.

The full configuration of this system was:

144 channels of inputs for test article sensors
48 channels of inputs for acoustic test microphones
24 acoustic outputs for driving the acoustic test system

Rack-mounted m+p International VibRunner IO's dedicated to the test system were connected to a large-scale Ethernet switch with a high-bandwidth (10G) backbone. 1G ports were utilized for each respective VibRunner, while 10G ports were loaded with standard Small Form-factor Pluggable (SFP) cards that enabled the connection of fiber optic cabling. A fiber optic cable was run from the DAS at the test circle to the ARS Drive rack in the control area. By utilizing matching network switches at both the test circle end and the test control end of the fiber optic run, a bi-directional 10G connection could be maintained between the test setup and the control area. The computers utilized to operate the combined control + data acquisition system was fitted with the correct Ethernet cards to ensure that a 10G connection was maintained. Acoustic outputs for driving the DFAN system were connected into a co-located DirectOut Prodigy.MP audio processor for digital distribution to amplifiers.

5. SETUP & DEPLOYMENT OF TEST SYSTEM

Following a detailed and collaborative process to ensure that all parties supporting the DFAN test campaign reviewed, contributed, and signed off on the finalized design and ConOps for the DFAN test configuration, the actual installation and setup of the DFAN test was undertaken. There were several key areas of the system installation and setup that are noteworthy due to their importance for ensuring a safe and efficient deployment:

1. Simplification of control and configuration
2. Novel operational assets for support functions
3. Detailed procedural documentation for stacking
4. Implementation of system-wide grounding plan

5.1 Simplification of Control & Configuration

One of the first areas of note is the simplification of the test control strategy, and the impact of that simplification on the setup of the test. While previously published, literature has discussed the importance of control strategies for

acoustic testing [6], often the impact of the chosen control strategy on how the acoustic test system is wired and connected is not covered. In the interest of providing a holistic view of the acoustic test, the relationship between drive methodology and system installation merits discussion. Previously published literature from the authors [7] discusses the development of a novel acoustic device, which enables the usage of multiple stochastic, uncorrelated full-range noise signals to drive each acoustic device. Where narrowband control was the sole control method available at the time NASA Handbook 7010 was published, 1/3Octave-band control has come into use in recent years, its qualification and validation are discussed suitably in other works [4].

Previously published works cited the need to create different radial zones of mid-high loudspeakers, sub-bass loudspeakers [3], and then blend various drive signals together to drive a very large number of acoustic devices with a small number of drive signals. In the deployment discussed here, 1/3Oct MIMO control is utilized, creating functional blocks or “zones” in the test setup by utilizing one drive signal to drive one pair of vertically adjacent acoustic devices. This is repeated throughout the test setup, with each block of acoustic devices utilizing a drive signal completely uncorrelated from the others. This simplification of the control strategy provides the following real-world operational improvements:

- Reduces physical connections required from amplifiers to acoustic devices.
- Reduces acoustic devices required.
- Reduces time to connect all devices in the test.
- Reduces the sensitivity of microphone placements.

While these benefits might not tie directly to acoustic field quality, they provide clear, measurable improvements in reducing setup time, which is a critical part of DFAN test campaign. The approach described above also reduces the likelihood of configuration errors, and it significantly reduces critical operations such as lifts, ladder climbs, and personnel activities around partially constructed configurations. While direct comparison between different DFAN systems is not easily made, a list of activities and completion times from this case study is below as **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 1: Select key test operations, typical time and staffing requirements to complete.

Build 6-High Column w/ Microphones & Cabling	20 Min.	4 People
Unload Four Tractor Trailers and Place Equipment	90 Min.	10 People

Complete Cabling for 48 Devices & 8 Amplifier Racks	120 Min.	6 People
Calibrate 45 microphones	20 Min.	2 People
Complete 60 Sec. Test Run (Self-Check to Test Complete)	3 Min.	N/A
Prepare Quick-Look Data for Post-Test Review	5 Min.	N/A
Unstack Complete Column and Remove Cabling	15 Min.	4 People
Complete Load-Out from Break Config to Last Truck Finished	6 Hrs.	6-10 People

5.2 Utilization of Novel Operational Assets

Two key operational assets were utilized for this test campaign. The first was a Microphone Support System (MSS), an asset that utilizes the acoustic device as a base for attaching critical test instrumentation. Often the floor of the test area becomes cluttered with cabling and stands required to place microphones in the field. This clutter can cause trip hazards, tip-over concerns, and increases the complexity of spatial navigation for technicians working around sensitive hardware. To reduce these risks, the MSS was designed and deployed with the goal of eliminating the floor footprint required for supporting the microphones used to conduct a DFAN test.

Figure 4: MSS installed for a demonstration.

Each MSS element can be pre-attached to the acoustic devices on the ground prior to the system being stacked. This means that columns of acoustic devices can be built with hardware already safely mounted, bolts torqued to spec, and all microphones pre-positioned to their correct location. This significantly reduces the amount of time required to configure the acoustic test system and reduces the number of trips technicians are required to make into the test circle for microphone installation and calibration.

5.3 Detailed Procedural Documentation for Stacking

The second key operational asset was a detailed procedural document for stacking. The preparation of a detailed procedure for a complex, critical environmental test is not a new topic. However, given the scope of this test campaign and the number of parties collaborating on its successful outcome, more attention needed to be paid to certain portions of the test configuration. This would help to ensure that the risks, safety requirements, and correct steps for the system to be deployed were all clearly understood.

6.2. Close Speaker Circle

Use the following steps to close the speaker circle.

	Action	Comment(s)	Buyoff
1	Move NEUTRON base plates from the storage area to the spiked locations at the speaker circle.		
2	Place NEUTRON base plates in proper position and replace shims (if any).		
3	If the overhead microphones were coiled back to the overhead line, remove zip tie/tape and allow microphone to hang vertically.		
4	Instruct crane operator to position crane to be able to lift NEUTRON stack #4.		
5	Using personnel lift, attach crane hook to the NLF master ring.		
6	Instruct crane operator to lift stack slightly (roughly 6 inches).		
7	Instruct crane operator to translate load to the preset base plate for NEUTRON stack #4.		
8	Instruct crane operator to gently lower load onto base plate. Alignment fins in the speaker and base plate will aid in placement.		
9	Using personnel lift, remove crane hook from NLF. Place NLF master ring inside of NLF.		
10	Instruct crane operator to position crane to be able to lift NEUTRON stack #5.		
11	Using personnel lift, attach crane hook to the NLF master ring.		
12	Instruct crane operator to lift stack slightly (roughly 6 inches).		
13	Instruct crane operator to translate load to the preset base plate for NEUTRON stack #5.		
13	Instruct crane operator to gently lower load onto base plate. Alignment fins in the speaker and base plate will aid in placement.		
14	Using personnel lift, remove crane hook from NLF. Place NLF master ring inside of NLF.		
15	Connect NEUTRON Up cables to the associated NEUTRON Down cables at the base of NEUTRON stack #4 and NEUTRON stack #5.		
16	Connect all microphone cabling from microphones mounted on NEUTRON stack #4 and NEUTRON stack #5. This connection will be made at the BNC connectors on the associated microphone sub box.		

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Figure 5: Example from test procedure illustrating detailed stacking operations and signoffs.

Shown in Figure 5 is an example from one portion of the procedure, which illustrates the importance of detailing each step in the assembly process. It is critical to ensure from the very onset of the setup process that not only are all physical connections made safely and correctly, but there are error proofing and traceability steps created along the way. This way, when the system is powered up and checked out, the risk of incorrect connections can be significantly mitigated, if not eliminated, making a notable contribution to the success of the test as well as the timeliness of its safe execution.

5.4 Implementation of Systemwide Grounding Plan

With the implementation of a large-scale data acquisition system – providing a potential connection from flight hardware to DFAN system hardware –

running simultaneously with the acoustic test control system, proper grounding was identified as a critically important topic early in the design process. There are several elements in play that need to be considered when designing a plan to safely ground and acoustic test system.

- Mains power: Grounding for the generator or facility power source for the DFAN system
- Power distribution: Grounding for the equipment providing an electrical path between devices
- Ancillary power: Grounding for sources powering the control and data acquisition system.

3.4. Acoustic device array in wave6

The calibration data and acoustic device geometry for an ARS NEUTRON acoustic device is included in the wave software. The software also contains functionality for quickly creating and calibrating DFAN arrays. Fig. 8 shows an example of a wave6 model of the validation test discussed in subsequent sections.

Figure 6: Simplified diagram of system grounding plan.

Each of these subsystems needs to be reviewed regarding where they connect with each other, where they ground to, and how that grounding interacts with the grounding configuration of the test article. For the test described here, the teams were able to collaborate on a plan that ensured the test article, attached support equipment, sensors, and the connected elements of the DFAN system were all grounded correctly. This successfully eliminated potential sources of noise, interference, and other electrical phenomena with no issues seen during testing.

6. TEST EXECUTION & SAFETY

A test campaign was scheduled in collaboration between the DFAN system vendor, spacecraft prime contractor, and host facility support teams. A conservative, nine-day schedule was targeted, which is illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.** There can be additional complexity in the establishment of a DFAN test schedule when compared to other environmental tests, as the portable nature of a DFAN system can require the scheduling of trucking, key support staff, and facility spaces that might not typically be occupied for multi-day test campaigns. These additional scheduling considerations also might need to be looked at in the context of other operations in the test campaign such as test data analysis, program approval meetings, or other facility operations that might conflict with resources needed for the DFAN test.

Table 2: Example multi-day test schedule.

Day 1	Unload Trucks
	Stack Acoustic Devices
	Deploy Racks of Amplifiers
	Perform Initial System Cabling
Day 2	Complete System Cabling
	Connect and Calibrate Microphones
	Perform Bare Chamber Test Runs
Day 3	Break Configuration, Install Flight Hardware
	Connect Flight Hardware Instrumentation
	Restore Configuration
Day 4	Perform -9dB Test Run
Day 5	Perform -6dB Test Run
Day 6	Perform -3dB Test Run
Day 7	Perform 0dB and -9dB Test Runs
Day 8	Break Configuration, Remove Hardware
	Begin to de-cable and pack up electronics
Day 9	Complete unstacking and load trucks

A key consideration for DFAN test scheduling is the amount of time required to perform post-test data analysis by the required parties. DFAN is not unique when it comes to the balancing of program schedule goals with the analysis time required to review post-test results and provide safe-to-proceed guidance. For DFAN, there typically needs to be additional consideration for the scheduling of support personnel, and cumulative delays to the program can adversely impact the scheduling of support services such as equipment transportation. As illustrated above (**Error! Reference source not found.**), the actual time required to conduct a 60-second test run at a given level is typically less than 3 minutes. However, this means that a great deal of the schedule between test runs can be dictated by factors outside of the control of the DFAN test program itself.

6.1 Test Safety & Facility Impact

On the topic of test safety, from the standpoint of executing the test campaign, several key areas were addressed:

- Prediction of acoustic levels away from test
- Pre-task briefings following a set guideline as an error prevention method before each test run
- Implementation of redundant abort capabilities

Prior to the commencement of the test campaign, several studies had been undertaken to provide rough predictions of how the acoustic energy generated by the DFAN test system might dissipate through the walls and across the floors of the large host facility. While the bulk of this material is covered in other work [8], for the sake of this case study it is worth noting that:

- Simple inverse square calculations can be utilized to roughly estimate how acoustic energy might dissipate over distance inside a building.
- Sound Transmission Class (STC) and Noise Reduction Coefficient (NRC) ratings, applied to materials noted in the documentation of the host facility, can help to provide rough estimates of how a facility structure might affect the dissipation of acoustic energy.
- In general, acoustic loss over distance seen in large, long high-bay areas tends to measure between 3dB and 6dB in loss per doubling of distance.

Figure 7: Simplified diagram of predicted A-weighted OASPL levels at key facility locations.

If an area of the host facility was noted to likely require personal protective equipment (PPE) during an acoustic test run, then the individuals working in that area would need to be warned of an impending test, given time to apply PPE, and any impacts to critical operations such as lifting activities would need to be noted and resolved prior to the start of an acoustic test run.

6.2 Safety Abort Interlocks

The final item of note from an operational safety standpoint is the implementation of multi-stage, redundant abort capabilities. For the test described here, the following interlocks were utilized to mitigate the risk of anomalous acoustical emissions from the DFAN system during all phases of test:

- Digital mutes in audio processor
- Digital mutes in audio amplifiers
- Acoustic controller abort
- Amplifier safety abort interlock

The amplifier safety abort interlock is a new capability integrated for this test. It comprises of two key parts. First, each amplifier in the system comes with a GPIO (General Purpose Input Output) interface [9], the GPIO's of all amplifiers in the system can be wired together as part of a pre-designed rack interface system. Second, a handheld controller featuring an integrated power supply was designed and outfitted with a connection interface to provide an uninterruptible connection to the GPIO circuitry of all the amplifiers in the system. Through the application of a constant voltage via the handheld controller to the GPIO of every amplifier, a circuit on each amplifier is activated that shuts down the amplification stage of the amplifier, immediately ceasing the output of any signal. This capability provides an additional level of safety beyond digital audio mutes and controller aborts as it is a physical, analog connection to all devices.

Figure 8: Handheld safety abort switch.

It ensures that before a test, during any time personnel are present, or during a test run with sensitive hardware, if at any point an abort that cuts the output of the audio system can be called and triggered almost instantaneously. This circuit can also be used preemptively. Whenever personnel are working in the test circle and the system is in its powered state, the risk of damage from unplanned transients or operator errors can be mitigated by placing the system in an “abort active” state until the work is completed, and the circle is again clear of personnel.

7. DFAN TEST CAMPAIGN RESULTS

To conduct the test, a system of 48 purpose-built, full-range ARS Neutron™ acoustic devices were deployed in an 8x6 configuration – eight columns around and six devices high – on a 6m diameter circle. The system was driven with 24 uncorrelated drive signals, each drive fed digitally to two multi-channel amplifiers each via the Dante™ Audio-Over-IP protocol. A 1/3Oct MIMO control scheme was used with a one-second control loop time. The use of uncorrelated noise outputs fed to full-range acoustic devices has been demonstrated in previously published material to provide acoustic field uniformity and diffusivity characteristics that are ideal for acoustic testing. [4] The system utilized 24 control microphones, and 21 monitor microphones were deployed at key locations around the test setup. All microphones were PCB 378A12's. Note that three monitor microphones were deployed in enclosed cavities within and around the test article, labeled M12 through M14, they are included in the plots below for the sake of completeness but were not utilized for field evaluation.

Figure 9: DFAN system in bare chamber configuration.

Following the installation and connection of the DFAN system, a loop check was performed utilizing the acoustic controller. This provides verification of each individual control loop. Each drive output is fed with a short noise signal, its routing to amplifiers can be verified, and noise emits at a low level (~100dB) from each acoustic device. The controller receives the output of the loop check signal via individual control microphones assigned to each pair of acoustic devices and provides a confirmation of the correlation of drive outputs to control microphone inputs. This process takes approximately 5 seconds per output, for a total of 120 seconds of time to complete a loop check.

The appropriate procedural steps to ensure readiness of the test system and facility were taken, and clearance was given to perform the bare chamber runs. These runs are critical to ensuring that the DFAN system can perform the specified acoustic test levels, and they offer an opportunity to verify power, signal routing, and facility acoustic levels. The first bare chamber run was performed at a -20dB level (~120dB), which enabled staff to traverse the test facility and take handheld measurements of sound pressure levels at key areas while the run was active. This information was used primarily for the purpose of validating the predicted facility sound pressure levels from early in the design process. For the sake of this case study, it can be noted that measured sound pressure levels outside the test area were typically within ~1dB of predicted sound levels. This verification of levels helped to inform decisions regarding where personnel could work, what PPE would be required, and what times that runs could be conducted to ensure the lowest impact to other programs working in the facility.

Figure 10: Simplified diagram of measured A-weighted OASPL levels at key facility locations.

7.1 Combined Bare Chamber Runs

The next set of bare chamber runs were conducted to verify achievement of test level and field uniformity. An approach was employed in which all bare chamber levels (-9dB, -6dB, -3dB, and 0dB) were verified in a single run. Following initial low-level equalization of the DFAN system, the system was scheduled to run for 30 seconds at each level prior to 0dB, and then for the full 120 seconds at 0dB required by the test program. Because the system can rise in level linearly and arrive at the scheduled level without needing additional equalization, there is no risk of under- or over-shoot at the start of each test level. This means that the analysts reviewing the bare chamber data could have 30 seconds of level-correct data for each preliminary level, and then the full 120 seconds of time history data at the 0dB level to review and verify uniformity, diffusivity, and stability. This approach also saved significant time vs. legacy methods, as the entire bare chamber series could be completed safely and effectively in under five minutes. The use of quick-look plots enabled the required test personnel to make an expedient decision regarding

the approval to proceed (ATP), and once ATP was given the configuration was broken to install the flight hardware for test.

7.2 ConOps For Intermediary Configuration

The process of moving the acoustic devices and making the test setup ready for installation of flight hardware took approximately 90 minutes, and the restoration of the DFAN system following installation of flight hardware also took 90 minutes. It should be noted, as discussed previously, that calculations had been made to determine the stability not only the fully constructed DFAN system, but also the various partial configurations that were encountered as part of the hardware installation process. These calculations determined that the individual columns of acoustic devices were stable on their own, due in large part to their inherently stable design and the low risk of seismic activity in the region of the test. No counterweights were required for columns, and only one crane was required.

Following the installation of flight hardware, acoustic testing commenced. Due to the proprietary nature of the unit under test, the details of the structural response under test cannot be fully elucidated in this case study. However, the 0dB run will be discussed from the standpoint of DFAN system performance.

The requisite procedural steps to ensure that the unit under test was in a ready state for testing were undertaken, then room clears were given, and safety notifications were made in the facility regarding the use of PPE. The full-level test was then ready to proceed. As with all test runs, a low-level loop check was performed to ensure DFAN system readiness. When the test commenced, the DFAN system came on and equalized at a -15dB level for ~15 seconds. It then ramped in level to -3dB and equalized for ~10 seconds. Then the controller ramped to 0dB and within ~5 seconds began the 0dB run. The 0dB level was held for 120 seconds.

7.3 Power Monitoring Results

During the 0dB run, an Amprobe DM-5 Power Quality Monitor was used to monitor the generator powering the DFAN system. A 150kW generator was chosen for this test as suitable facility power was not conveniently co-located to the test. During the spacecraft 0dB run the DFAN system used an average of 25 amps per line. Utilizing a 3-phase 415/240V mains power supply, this means that the DFAN system needed approximately 20kVa of power to achieve the ~141dB specification. The following plots show power usage and quality captured during the spacecraft 0dB run.

Figure 11: Current draw for 48 amplifier system.

Figure 12: Voltage for 48 amplifier system. Note voltage rising as generator compensated for demand.

Figure 13: Total harmonic distortion for each line.

7.4 Acoustic Field Measurements

The DFAN test campaign ran to schedule, and all metrics for acoustic field quality and spacecraft structural response were met or exceeded. The plots that follow show various metrics that were presented to confirm that the acoustic field met the target specification at a wide range of locations both horizontally and vertically around the test article, confirmed by a mix of both control microphones (actively participating in test control) and monitor microphones (not in control loop).

It is worth noting the number of monitor microphones used for the test was arrived at using a combination of:

- Input from the spacecraft prime contractor as to sensitive areas they were interested in studying
- Suggested areas based on best practices and experiences from the DFAN system vendor
- Physical limitations incurred due to the placement of the unit under test and the space left available.

The goal of utilizing a significant number of monitor microphones is to help ensure that the acoustic field is meeting the desired criteria at a diverse set of points around the unit under test, and not only at a few select control points.

Acoustic measurements for the 0dB run follow. All measurements utilize a linear average of the entire test time at the 0dB level (120 seconds). Note for monitor microphone plots that M12-M14 were placed outside of the acoustic field and in an enclosure during the test runs. However, they are included in these plots for the sake of completeness.

Figure 14: Spacecraft 0dB run, control mics. 1/3Oct

Figure 15: Spacecraft 0dB run, monitor mics. 1/3Oct. Note M12-M14 outside of acoustic field.

Figure 16: Spacecraft 0dB run, control mics, PSD.

Figure 17: Spacecraft 0dB run, monitor mics, PSD. Note M12-M14 outside of acoustic field.

Figure 20: Coherence between mics for bare chamber.

Figure 21: Coherence between mics for spacecraft.

Figure 22: Deviation per 1/3Oct band, 0dB runs for control mics comparing bare chamber to spacecraft.

Figure 23: Deviation per 1/3Oct band 0dB runs, for monitor mics comparing bare chamber to spacecraft.

CONCLUSION & FORWARD WORK

Following the completion of the test presented here, it can be stated that all structural responses were analyzed and found to be within expected ranges, especially when responses were compared to those the same driven by diffuse acoustic field conditions in simulation. All acoustic test success criteria were met, and the campaign was completed without incident. The flight hardware was qualified for the selected launch vehicle. Due to the proprietary nature of the hardware under test, more information is not available currently. However, it is the authors hope that in time more detailed structural response data can be released for the sake of enhancing this publication in the future.

This case study of a DFAN system comprising 48 acoustic devices also served as a key step towards the future deployment of a larger configuration of 90 acoustic devices, which will support the testing of a 10m tall payload. Following the completion of that significantly larger test campaign, the publication of an additional case study is planned.

While DFAN has been a topic of interest since the 1990's, material published on DFAN test operations and safety has been limited despite DFAN's unique, portable nature. Acoustic field generation and qualification are of the utmost importance to assuring a successful DFAN test campaign, but if a system cannot be designed, constructed, and operated in a safe and efficient manner, its acoustical performance is effectively a moot point. If the larger industry does not widen its field of view to see DFAN testing and DFAN test systems as more than simply microphone measurements and control algorithms, then the benefits of the approach will continue to be weighed down by unforeseen operational challenges, personnel and facility safety concerns, and a lack of clear guidance on non-acoustical topics.

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